

Effects of Convergent and Divergent Instructional Strategies on Achievement in Basic Technology among Secondary School Students in Calabar Municipal

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ABSTRACT

The study intends to investigate effects of convergent and divergent instructional strategies on achievement in basic technology among secondary school students in Calabar municipal. Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest - posttest non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study. The sample size of the study consists of 120 upper Basic class three (JSS3) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Calabar municipal, Cross River State. The participants first took a pre-test after which they were divided into three groups for the treatment. After the treatment, each group took a posttest to demonstrate the extent of understanding the materials learnt. The data was analyzed using ANCOVA and Post Hoc analysis. The study revealed that students exposed to divergent strategy have high performance in basic technology than those taught using convergent strategy. It was further recommended that teachers should be encouraged on the use of divergent instructional strategy in the teaching and learning of Basic Technology

Keyword: Convergent instruction, divergent instruction, electricity.

Introduction

Education is often regarded as an instrument for social, economic, scientific and technological development. Nigeria as a country desirous of wholistic development is doing everything possible to provide the needed education for her citizen

In Nigeria, and almost at all level of education, there is a repositioning in favour of an education that ensures, job-creation, self-employment and wealth creation. At the Basic level of education, vocational education is one aspect that is designed to develop skills, abilities, understanding, attitudes, work habits and self-reliance. One of the pre-vocational subjects offered at this level is Basic technology; which is to provide knowledge in woodwork, metal work, technical drawing, 'auto-mechanic' and electricity and electronics (Ohikehemg, 1994). It is an aspect of education that attempts to provided learning experience that would assist students in understanding the industrial and technological aspect of life.

According to the National Policy on Education (2004), Basic technology is a phase of general education designed to introduced the learner to and acquaint him/her with the basic process, material and product of the industries. In other words, it is intended to reduce ignorance about technological education. Specially, the objectives are: (i) To provide pre-vocational orientation for further training into technology; (ii) To provide basic technology literacy for everyday living, and (iii) To inculcate creativity

It is however, surprising that despite the efforts of government, good spirited individuals and non-governmental agencies to enhancing educational development at this level, the general performance in Basic

technology is not encouraging. Reports from different States of Nigeria indicated poor performance of students in their Junior Secondary School Examination in the subject (Nwoji, 2000; Lenda, 2001 & Igberadja, 2015). With this abysmal performance, it is doubtful if the students can even interpret simple machine drawings, carry out simple production of light using battery and wire, or even simple maintenance of motor vehicle or whether they have even acquired appropriate job training and experience in any of the specific trades.

Many factors have been implicated for the abysmal performance of students in Basic technology examination (Okebukola & Jegede, 1986; Adejoh, 2006; Igberadja, 2015). These include: inability of the teacher to put across the concepts to the students; lack of skills and competence required for teaching and shortage of qualified teachers. Similarly, Nwodo (1997), Jati (2003), Omalle and Okedi (2008) all opined that the poor performance of students in basic technology may be due to the use of inappropriate teaching methods.

There is therefore need for the continuous search for the most effective approach to the teaching and learning of this important subject, that will enhance students understanding and application of learnt concepts and principles, and such searches have resulted in the development of student centered instructional approaches such as divergent method, among others. Okri, Joy and Peter (2021) investigated the effectiveness of classroom environment and SSII students report of avoidance strategy in Mathematics in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State. A sample of 300 SS II Students, (150 males and 150 females) was used for the study. Propulsive multistage random sampling technique (stratified and simple random sampling) was used to composed the sample. Three research questions were answered and three hypotheses were tested in the study at $p < 0.05$. Questionnaire was used to collect the data. The obtained data was analysed using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA). It was found that student classroom truancy significantly influences students report of avoided strategy in Mathematics performance. In another study, Okri and Aglazor (2020) conducted a study effectiveness of three instructional strategies in the improvement of senior secondary students' performance in geometry in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State. Four schools were sampled consist of 150 senior secondary school (SS II) students (77 females and 73 males) with an average age of 15 years participated in the study. A validated instrument titled Geometry Performance Test (GPT) was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was established using Kuder-Richardson, KR-21 to obtain an index of 0.84. Five research questions and five hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA) at .05 level of significance. The findings indicated that the highest performance gain was made by students taught using hands-on instructional strategy (HIS) and co-operative instructional strategy (CPIS). There were no significance relative main effects on gender on the GPT score on students taught using HIS, CPIS and COLIS respectively. There was a significant difference among the three instructional strategies with respect to GPT scores of students. It was recommended among others that Mathematics teachers should endeavor to adopt both strategies in the delivery of geometry concepts in Mathematics instructions in the senior secondary schools in Nigeria.

Studies abound which attest to the relative effectiveness of the divergent approach in facilitating students' technology concepts attainment (Waine, 2010 & Reintelman, 2007). Commenting on the effect of teaching strategies, Steadman (1994) & Anyafulude (2007) both affirmed superiority of divergent strategy to the convergent strategy in students' achievement. Divergent instruction strategy is simply a method where the students are asked to produce as many solutions to a problem as they probably can. It involves open ended questions and students-centered, involving divergent thinking. On the other hand, convergent instructional strategy is a common teaching method where the teacher transmits the necessary information to the students. The students engage in convergent thinking, where they draw on their prior knowledge to answer mostly closed-ended questions.

It is against this backdrop that this present study sought to examine the effects that convergent and divergent instructions have on students' understanding/ of electricity principles which is an aspect of Basic technology in order to provide scope and direction. In this study, the comparative effect of the two instructional strategies (convergent and divergent) on students' achievement and understanding of some electricity principles was the focus.

Research Hypothesis

The Following research hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of basic technology students taught the concept electricity using convergent instructional strategies and those exposed to divergent instructional strategies among upper basic schools in calabar municipal.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design. Specifically, pre-test, posttest non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study. The sample consisted of 120 JSS3 Basic technology students in selected schools in the study area during the 2023/2024 academic session. The students were drawn from three intact classes randomly drawn from a clustered sample of three Junior Secondary in Calabar Municipal.

The validated instrument was developed by one of the researchers who is an expert in measurement and evaluation. These include the pre-achievement test in some electricity principles, post achievement test and a test to determine their understanding of what was taught. The experimental groups were taught some electricity principles by the researchers using convergent and divergent strategies while the control was taught by their regular teacher using his usual/ conventional method. After 4 weeks, the post achievement test in electricity was administered to the students. Two weeks after the administration of the post achievement, the test to determine understanding was administered. In this case, the post - test was re-administered to assess understanding of basic principles of electricity. The instrument's reliability was 0.76 using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The resulting scores were analysed using SPSS. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of probability using ANCOVA.

Results

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of basic technology students taught the concept electricity using convergent instructional strategies and those exposed to divergent instructional strategies among upper basic schools in calabar metropolis.

To test this hypothesis, the analysis of covariance was used and the results are shown in Table 1. The result of the analysis of covariance shown in Table 1 revealed a significant F- ratio of 15.66 at .05 level of significance with 2 degrees of freedom. This indicates that the calculated f-ratio is statistically significant. In other words, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. With the rejection of the null, the alternate hypothesis which states that There is significant difference in mean achievement scores of basic technology students taught the concept electricity using convergent instructional strategies and those exposed to divergent instructional strategies among upper basic schools in calabar metropolis is hereby retained.

TABLE 1: Analysis of covariance of students Mean understanding scores classified by treatment groups with pre-test as covariate

Sources of variation	SS	Df	Ms	F	Sig
Covariate	2613.40	1	2613.40	*36.42	.000
Main effect	2098.80	2	1049.40	*15.66	.004
Explained	4712.31	3	1570.77	*17.43	.005
Resident	14552.70	116	125.433		
Total	19265.01	119			

To determine the direction of the difference in the mean understanding scores of students in the three teaching strategies (convergent, divergent and conventional) the Scheffe's test was applied and the result is as shown in Table 2. The result in Table 2 showed a significant means difference of 7.40 and 10.02 indicating that students taught with divergent method have higher mean performance score than those taught using convergent and conventional strategies, respectively. On the other hand, the non-significant difference of 1.29 indicates that students taught with convergent method were not better than those taught with the conventional method.

Discussion of Findings

The result shows that students taught with divergent strategy had higher mean performance score in concept electricity than those taught with convergent and the control group.

This finding is in agreement with those Steadman (1994) Anyafulude (2007), Reintelman (2007) and Waine (2010). Of course, this result was expected as those studies were all in the area of science. However, this finding disagrees with Ofoterbi (1990) who observed that convergent and expository were equally effective. This lack of difference may be due to the fact that both expository and convergent strategies do not involve students in the brainstorming associated with divergent strategy (Anyafulude, 2004).

Table 2: Scheffe's Post Hoc multiple comparison of students' mean understanding scores in some electricity principles test by teaching strategies

Dependent variables	Treatment		Mean difference (I-J)	SD Error	Sig
	(I)	(J)			
Achievement Scores	Convergent	Divergent	- 7.40*	2.12	.002
		Conventional	1.29	2.25	.076
Achievement Scores	Divergent	Convergent	7.40*	2.12	.002
		Conventional	10.02*	1.70	.004
Achievement Scores	Conventional	Convergent	1.29	2.25	.076
		Divergent	10.02*	1.70	.004

Conclusion

Based on the finding, it was concluded that divergent teaching strategy is more appropriate in improving performance in Basic Technology among upper basic students in calabar municipal, Cross River State.

Recommendations

- i. Teachers should be encouraged to explore both convergent and divergent instructional strategy by using the convergent strategy to introduce the foundational knowledge needed to solve problems; and thereafter use the divergent approach to make students more logical, creative, understand and retain concepts in Basic technology.
- ii. Teachers' training and retraining seminars should incorporate divergent and convergent strategies that have proved very effective in the teaching of technology related subjects.

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